

THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: In this thesis I tried to show the importance of interactive methods and the role of them in teaching foreign languages in various types of interactive activities. I pointed out some instructions of theoretical and practical materials to the academic lyceum foreign language teaching.

Key words: interactive, individually, communication, group work, interaction, classify, lingual, appointment, exchange.

As the great changes have been happening in any part of the life of human being, teaching system has also been involved and changed last decades. Especially teaching foreign languages requires lots of improvements and researches. Traditional teaching methods like grammar translation method, audio lingual or direct methods have become less active and it has changed into nontraditional ones. It can help to improve students all skills, increase communication among them, achieve goals. The main aim of these changes is to provide not teacher-centered but learner-centered lessons. In this case the role of group work activities has its own position.

Interaction patterns in English language teaching are the different ways for learners and the teacher can interact in class. Using right interactive pattern is a foundation of achieving a success in class. There are four types of interaction patterns: individual work, pair work, whole class working, group work.¹

Individual work is which the task is given by individually and this type is beneficial for the students who do not want to exchange or share opinion to others. Individual work can help students gain independence to think things through on their own; work at their own level, rather than having to adapt to suit their group members, get more comfortable taking actions on their own. But there are some disadvantages of this type: less communication and reduce student's speech, in individual work some students especially extroverts may feel a bit isolated.

Pair work is when the given activity or task is presented for two students. They can solve the task together and the answer is given with the partner. It can help the teacher to watch all pairs how much they are working and gives to the group motivation.

Whole class work is usually prepared the task for all students in the group and the students work all together. It is usually beneficial for using videos or audio materials and discussed in whole group. But it is sometimes not useful type of interaction pattern for the students who prefer to work by individually.

Group work is an interaction pattern which the class is divided into various groups (large or small groups). In this case the teacher can organize the activity, give instructions to the students and is always observer of the lesson. Best advantage of it there might be many solutions and answers to the given task, students can communicate each other in the language which they are working hard on it in order to learn it completely and it can improve their speaking skill.

Group work activities can help to the students to learn more appointments by communicating to the group members and select the best answer to the given task. So it's main use is considered as selecting, grading and presenting. Group members select the best solution, try to analyze and classify it then they can grade the answer which is selected and come to the one point by group members.

Look at the various patterns of interaction described above and note for each one how active the teacher and students are in their participation, using the following code: **TT**= Teacher very active, students only receptive ; **T**=Teacher very active, students mainly receptive; **TS**=Teacher and students fairly equally active; **S**=Students active, teacher mainly receptive ; **SS**=Students very active, teacher only receptive. As we classify these interaction patterns the best ways of teaching by modern technics the importance of TT or T is getting more passive nowadays. TS, S, SS are modern and useful for both teaching foreign languages and also learning them.² Every ESL teacher knows interactive method is necessary for language students. But sometimes we forget why we do and what we do. The True Value of interactive methods in ESL Class

Interactive methods have lots of advantages for students, so we can look through some of the big ones.

It is communicative. Students have to talk to each other, and that means they are using those language skills which they have been working so hard to learn. It can be too time-consuming for one teacher to get around to talking to every student individually, especially in larger classrooms.

It is project-based. They have to accomplish something rather than just complete fabricated exercises, which is more like real-life language use.

It reduces teacher talk time. We all strive to talk less and get our students talking more in class. Interactive methods are the perfect way to do this. Encouraging these relationships helps everyone and may be just what some of your students need to develop a lifelong friendship.³

It appeals to different learning styles. Some people learn best on their own, but there are others who learn better when they are interacting with other people. Meeting this learning need is essential for the success of those students.

So, interactive methods give learners exposure to a range of language items and language functions. Working in a group children are more engaged not only intellectually but emotionally as well. They have to think, contribute to the group, evaluate what other members of the group say, share information, ask friends for clarification, and prepare a presentation together. Students use and experiment with the language items they already know in order to develop fluency; they also use some items pre taught by the teacher or contributed by the members of the group to express themselves more fully and improve the quality of their performance.

Used literature:

¹ Lightbown Patsy M, Nina Spada. 1993. How languages are learned, Oxford University Press

² David Nunan. Language teaching methodology. A textbook for teachers

³ www.teachingenglish.org.uk/article/interaction-patterns